

PRACTICAL ASPECTS FOR USAGE FOR SOCIAL NETWORKS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM

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Abstract. The rise of social networks and global digitalization has brought about significant transformations across various aspects of society, including tourism. The growing prominence of information platforms with traveler-generated content has shifted scientific research towards understanding the pivotal role of social networks in travel planning. Social networks increasingly influence tourist decisions regarding destinations, accommodations, and types of travel experiences. The article examines the impact of social networks, such as travel blogs and forums, on contemporary society.

Keywords: travel blogs, forums, social networks marketing, business, internet.

Information technologies have contributed to the formation of a new type of tourists who independently choose destinations and create a package of services that they would like to receive. In addition, they can receive information not only from travel companies, but also from other tourists, for example, they can read reviews when choosing a particular service. With the advent of the Internet, tourists do not need live intermediaries - their role is performed by socio-technical networks [1]. Thus, people can book rooms on the websites of the hotels themselves. In addition, in addition to personal connections between people, which are usually used by supporters of the network approach, the analysis also includes participants in virtual communities - tourists take into account the opinions of not only their acquaintances, but also strangers who participate in the formation of ratings and reviews of certain tourist places.

Positive changes for the tourism and hotel business are also dictated by an increase in the share of the elderly population, including the working population, who have certain formed desires and intentions that they can realize, having an appropriate income. In many ways, this is facilitated by progress in the development of medical technologies, since members of society can maintain a certain quality of life and spend their leisure time for their own pleasure. Along with this, such a direction as medical tourism is actively developing, attracting the "age segment" of consumers who prefer to combine

rest with treatment and correction of their health condition. Another positive factor can be considered the population's focus on a healthy lifestyle, which contributes to the development of the organic food market and fitness club services. The same trend stimulates the development of active tourism, balanced loads during travel, etc. As one of the sub-directions in this direction, visiting "beauty farms" and various SPA-salons at famous resorts, on the territory of health resorts and simply outside the metropolises is developing, where services are offered to restore vitality, correct loads on the body, and restore natural biorhythms. In many ways, this offer is focused on the female target audience, which has recently become economically active and can independently plan and pay for their vacation.

When studying the modern world, researchers highlight its visualization and imagery as the leading features. The famous specialist in the field of visual culture M. Barnard notes: "What is visual has become an important experience in people's lives. We are increasingly influenced by visual materials and dependent on them" [4]. In this guise, modern reality is included in the subject field of scientific research. Scientists emphasize the dominance of visual media over oral and written messages, emphasize the importance of visual sensations and manifestations in everyday life [3]. This feature is also highlighted by domestic researchers: "Modern man perceives the entire surrounding world through the visual channel by means of visual images. The very way of presenting information has changed: preference has shifted from narrative to figurative". It is no coincidence that modern society is called a "community of massive imagery" [2]. Visualization and virtualization of reality have required unconventional ways of studying it. A new direction has emerged in science – visual research (in cultural anthropology, sociology, psychology), where photography becomes the leading object of study. The most prominent representative of visual sociology is the Polish sociologist P. Sztompka. The scientist shows the importance of visual representations in postmodern society and the role of photography in research. He believes that "a photographic image in the perspective of visual sociology is not only an independent object of cognition, but also a means of cognition of something greater, namely social life" [3].

Utilizing social networks effectively can significantly enhance the development of tourism. Here are practical aspects and strategies for leveraging social media in tourism development:

1. Creating a Strong Online Presence

- **Profile Optimization:** Ensure that your social media profiles are complete, professional, and engaging. Use high-quality images, detailed descriptions, and up-to-date information about your destination or business.
- **Consistent Branding:** Maintain a consistent brand voice and visual style across all social media platforms to build a recognizable and trustworthy presence.

2. Content Strategy and Creation

- **Engaging Content:** Share diverse content types, including stunning visuals, videos, travel stories, and behind-the-scenes looks. Highlight unique aspects of your destination or services.
- **User-Generated Content:** Encourage tourists to share their own experiences and tag your location or business. Repost user-generated content to build community and authenticity.
- **Local Stories:** Feature local culture, events, and attractions to provide a rich, immersive experience for your audience.

3. Targeted Advertising and Promotions

- **Ads and Sponsored Posts:** Use social media advertising tools to target specific demographics, interests, and locations. Promote special offers, packages, and events to reach potential tourists.
- **Influencer Collaborations:** Partner with travel influencers or bloggers to expand your reach. Influencers can provide authentic endorsements and attract their followers to your destination.

4. Engagement and Interaction

- **Responsive Communication:** Engage with followers by responding to comments, messages, and reviews promptly. Address inquiries and feedback to build positive relationships.
- **Interactive Content:** Use polls, quizzes, and live sessions to interact with your audience and encourage participation. This helps in understanding their preferences and interests.

5. Monitoring and Analytics

- **Track Metrics:** Use analytics tools provided by social media platforms to monitor engagement, reach, and effectiveness of your campaigns. Analyze metrics such as likes, shares, comments, and click-through rates.
- **Adjust Strategies:** Regularly review performance data to refine your content strategy, advertising efforts, and engagement tactics based on what resonates best with your audience.

6. Developing Community and Building Relationships

- **Fostering a Community:** Create and nurture online communities where travelers can share experiences, ask questions, and connect with others. Consider creating groups or forums related to specific interests or destinations.
- **Local Partnerships:** Collaborate with local businesses, attractions, and influencers to cross-promote and enhance your tourism offerings. Joint promotions and events can attract more attention and visitors.

7. Crisis Management and Reputation Control

- **Proactive Monitoring:** Monitor social media channels for mentions and reviews related to your destination or business. Address any negative feedback or crises quickly and professionally.
- **Positive Engagement:** Highlight positive reviews and testimonials to build a strong reputation and showcase customer satisfaction.

8. Content Scheduling and Consistency

- **Regular Posting:** Develop a content calendar to ensure consistent posting and keep your audience engaged. Schedule posts to align with peak times when your audience is most active.
- **Seasonal and Event-Based Content:** Tailor your content to align with seasonal trends, local events, and holidays to capture timely interest and relevance.

9. Innovative Uses of Technology

- **Augmented Reality (AR):** Implement AR features in social media apps to offer virtual tours or interactive experiences of your destination.
- **Virtual Reality (VR):** Share VR content to provide immersive previews of destinations or attractions, enticing potential tourists with virtual experiences.

10. Educational and Informational Content

- **Travel Tips and Guides:** Share practical travel tips, local guides, and informative content to help tourists plan their visits and enhance their travel experience.
- **Safety Information:** Provide up-to-date information on health, safety, and travel guidelines to reassure and inform travelers.

By effectively utilizing these practical aspects, tourism organizations can leverage social media to enhance visibility, engage with potential tourists, and drive growth in the tourism sector.

In summary, social media has become a central element in modern tourism, shaping how travelers discover, plan, and experience their trips. It serves as a

powerful tool for inspiration, marketing, customer engagement, and real-time interaction.

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